

Discovering regularities implicated in scientific reward activities: A multi-dimensional observation from F-L-P-T awards

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Abstract

Despite scientific awards have received increasing interest of researchers, studies involving the regularities implicated in scientific reward activities aimed at combining multiple dimensions with ‘award distribution, award age, award delay, and award field’ have not yet been sufficiently performed. To address this limitation, this study focused on high prestige scientific awards and selected four awards (F-L-P-T) from different S&T fields as empirical objects for a multi-dimensional quantitative analysis. The study revealed several regularities and characteristics of scientific reward activities, such as Pareto's law of the distribution of winners, award aging, award delay, innovation peak age in scientific discovery and periodicity of award fields. By uncovering these regularities, we can gain a better understanding of scientific discovery and its characteristics, which could inform evidence-based policies for research evaluation and talent cultivation.

Introduction

Under the current trend of globalization of scientific research and internationalization of academic communications, scientific awards, as a kind of consensus affirmation, praise, and incentive for specific scientific discoveries in the scientific community, possess authority, fairness, and widespread recognition. In the 1950s and 1960s, the sociology of science was born as an independent discipline, and one of its critical research topics is the reward system of science (Merton, 1957, 1973). Moreover, Jonathan R. Cole and Stephen Cole (1973), the prominent scholars of the Merton School, conducted research on the functioning of the social stratification in science and the reward system in science. In particular, as the first researcher to study Nobel laureates, Zuckerman (1977) visualized the stratification structure in science as a pyramid, with a large number of ordinary scientists at the bottom and those of high reputation and academic prestige at the top. Zuckerman proposed that Nobel laureates represent the "super elites" of science, as determined by the stratification in science.

The constructing of the scientific social system relies on the reward system of science as its foundation. The functions of scientific awards can be summarized as follows: (1) the confirmation of the priority of scientific discovery; (2) the recognition of academic contributions; (3) the scientific community consensus on the direction of the academic field; (4) the incentive for the scientific community; (5) the awarding party (individuals, foundations, etc.) achieve their own value pursuit or the goal of S&T governance (governments, etc.). Scientific awards could reflect the stratification process that already exists in the scientific community. Research on scientific awards, which has become a primary means for the scientific community to assess significant S&T developments, is also an valuable perspective to observing the growth of talent and the scientific system.

Since the 20th century, worldwide scientific awards have been vigorously enriched (Ma and Uzzi, 2018), and scientific awards have received increasing attention from researchers. Relevant studies have been performed within fields such as sociology of science (O'Sullivan, 2001; Chan and Torgler, 2015), bibliometrics and scientometrics (Garfield, 1977; Gingras and Wallace, 2010; Frandsen and Nicolaisen, 2013), education (Wang, 2007; Bao et al., 2014), biomedicine (Rothenberg and Wyshak, 2004), and economics (Baffes and Vamvakidis, 2011; Doi, et al., 2014), involving many research perspectives such as award ranking (Zheng and Liu, 2015), spatiotemporal distribution (May, 1977; Ioannidis et al., 2020), citation analysis (Hu and Rousseau, 2017; Egghe, et al., 2011), academic relationship (Mukherjee et al., 2017; Chan et al., 2016), talent growth and flow (Wang et al., 2018), gender difference (Meho, 2021), award prediction (Sinatra et al, 2016), etc.

In addition, given the special status of the Nobel Prize, it is not surprising that previous studies have focused mostly on the Nobel Prize in science (Physics, Chemistry, and Physiology or Medicine). However, studies involving the regularities of scientific reward activities aimed at combining multiple dimensions with ‘award distribution, award age, award delay, award field, and collaboration pattern of achievements’ have not yet been sufficiently performed (Fig. 1), which could observe the reward regularities from the perspective of internal attributes and deepen the depth, breadth, and granularity of quantitative research in the sociology of science. Moreover, research and contrast in other domains of science (e.g., computer science, mathematics) have not yet been sufficiently done. Therefore, we start from the perspective of ‘high prestige scientific awards’ and focus on F-L-P-T awards (Fields Medal, Lasker Medical Research Award, Priestley Medal and Turing Award). Our purpose is to observe the common regularities implicated in scientific reward activities from a multi-dimensional perspective and to compare the differences between the disciplines of mathematics (F), biomedicine (L), chemistry (P) and computer science (T).

Figure 1. A multi-dimensional perspective to observe regularities of scientific awards.

Data and methodology

At present, there is no unified high reputation scientific awards database in the world. Some institutions rank the influence or reputation of scientific awards, including the ‘Official Awards Roster’ from the ICDA (1999), the ‘IREG List of International Academic Awards’ from IREG Observatory (2015), in which 99 international academic awards are selected, and NRC (National Research Council), which has identified 213 ‘prestigious’ awards to evaluate the quality and effectiveness of doctoral programs (Ostriker et al., 2011). Our investigation draws on three data sets, as shown in Figure 2.

- longitudinal F-L-P-T awards data, including award year, award list, and reasons.
- F-L-P-T prizewinners data such as the year of birth, nationality, institution.
- prizewinning papers of F-L-T prizewinners.

By the end of 2020, there were 61, 313, 84 and 74 F-L-P-T winners, respectively. The data sets were collected mainly from the official websites of awards (International Mathematical Union, The Lasker Foundation, American Chemical Society and Association for Computing Machinery), as well as homepages of F-L-P-T winners. In addition, we selected the Web of Science as the retrieval database (date of retrieval: December 2020).

Figure 2. F-L-P-T awards data collection process and primary items.

We took advantage of time series analysis and statistical analysis to study common regularities from the dimensions of spatiotemporal distribution, award age, and award delay and used qualitative cluster methods to analyse the evolution trend of the award field. Moreover, the collaboration network of prizewinning papers was analysed using bibliometric indicators (network density, centrality, etc.). In addition, the data cleaning and preprocessing of data sets were performed mainly with the help of DDA and Excel.

Findings

Our study reveals some scientific phenomena of scientific reward activities:

(1) The distribution of countries and institutions conforms to Pareto's law. Most scientists are distributed mainly in North America, Europe and other regions, especially major developed countries. The US tops the list with 367 winners, accounting for 68.98% of the total F-L-P-T winners, followed by the UK (44 winners), France (23 winners) and Germany (16 winners) (Fig. 3). Moreover, it can be clearly observed that as time goes backwards, the number of F-L-P-T winners in the US decreased from 97 during 1960-1979 to 89 during 2000-2020. Slight fluctuations in the number of winners are observed in France, the UK, Germany, and Japan. Most of the winners' affiliated institutions are 'leaders' in their corresponding fields. For example, 42 L winners work at Rockefeller University and Harvard University, which are the top biomedical centers in the world.

(2) There has been no significant change in the age of F winners due to the application requirement of 'under 40 years old', while the age of L-P-T scientists shows a significant aging trend, with an average increase of approximately 20 years since the first award. In the last five years, the average award age of L-P-T winners has even developed to 69.9, 70.6, 67.5 years old, respectively (Fig. 4a).

(3) There is a general award delay in the scientific reward system, but the time lag varies considerably between fields. F generally presented a trend of stable fluctuation (approximately 6 years). T showed a significant upwards trend, while the time lag for L-P winners was decreased year by year. Among them, Lasker scientific discoveries took 20.7 years to be recognized before 1935 to an average of 10.63 years since 2000, and P took 37.69 years to be recognized before 1935 to an average of 17.33 years since 1990 (Fig. 4b).

(4) We found that young and middle-aged scientists in the basic sciences, represented by mathematics, physiological medicine, chemistry and computer science, have greater ability and potential for innovation. The age of scientific discovery of F-L-P-T winners was concentrated between 31-50 years old (accounting for 71%), with an average age of 29.85, 42.79, 39.71, and 34.46 years old, respectively (Fig. 5).

Figure 3. National distribution of F-L-P-T winners and the trend of major countries.

(5) The award fields favored by F-L-P-T awards have periodic tendencies. Applied Mathematics (8.2%) has won few awards and has only begun to receive the attention of the Fields Award Committee since 1990. Regarding the Lasker prize, Molecular Biology (14.7%), Genetics (14.0%), and Clinical Pathology (20.5%) have the largest number of achievements, and most research fields have maintained innovative vitality in recent years. T prizewinning discoveries are mainly distributed in programming languages, algorithms and data structures, and artificial intelligence (accounting for more than 14%).

Furthermore, (6) we make a comparison in four disciplines, and the awarding regularities are different in different S&T fields.

Conclusion and discussion

In this paper, we selected four international prestigious scientific awards: Fields Medal in mathematics, Lasker Award in biomedicine, Priestley Medal in chemistry, and Turing Award in computer science as the key analysis objects. We carried out systematic and quantitative long-term data analysis to reveal some scientific phenomena or regularities implied in scientific awards, including the following: (1) a few countries and institutions have the most award winners (i.e., Pareto's law); (2) scientific award winners demonstrate the trends of award aging, award delay generally, and young and middle-aged innovation peak; (3) the award fields favored by scientific awards have periodic tendencies; and (4) the above award

regularities are diverse in different S&T disciplines, which have important implications for S&T policy and the development of S&T talent.

Figure 4. Award age (a) and time lag of scientific discoveries(b) of F-L-P-T winners.

Figure 5. The probability of the peak age (i.e., age of scientific discovery) of F-L-P-T winners.

In general, this paper conducted a multi-dimensional and multi-hierarchical analysis on the scientific reward activities represented by F-L-P-T awards. The findings could deepen researchers' understanding of the regularities governing scientific discoveries in related fields and provide evidence-based support for the improvement of policies for research funding and scientific evaluation. Especially in talent and project evaluation, it is necessary to consider the specificity of the disciplines, the periodicity of scientific discoveries, and the regularities of talent growth. Although the award fields are given out regularly, it is important to acknowledge that this regularity may not be a completely objective reflection of reality. Instead, it may be influenced by subjective factors such as the composition of the awarding committee, i.e., political or personal biases may play a role in determining which fields are recognized, and of course, it is also possible that the award's coverage itself contributes to this periodicity. In addition, it takes a certain time for scientific discovery to be picked up, and it takes longer for it to be recognized by the academic community (that is, to win awards). Therefore, the starting point of related S&T policy should be to encourage scientists to do continuous research and long-term accumulation, rather than to frequently assess and evaluate scientists.

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